

1 **Physical Activity Guideline Adherence and High-Impact Chronic Pain Among U.S. Adults:**
2 **A Cross-Sectional Analysis of the 2020 National Health Interview Survey**

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30 analysis was exempt from institutional review board approval per 45 CFR §46.101(b)(4).

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34 [nhis.html](https://www.cdc.gov/nchs/nhis/documentation/2020-nhis.html). The analytic code used to produce the reported results is available at
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44 **Abstract:**

45 Purpose: To examine the dose–response relationship between physical activity (PA) guideline
46 adherence and high-impact chronic pain (HICP) prevalence among U.S. adults.

47 Design: Cross-sectional secondary analysis.

48 Setting: 2020 National Health Interview Survey (NHIS), the only publicly available NHIS year
49 containing both HICP assessment items and detailed PA measures in the same adult sample.

50 Sample: 27,068 adults aged ≥ 18 years with complete data on PA, HICP, and covariates,
51 representing approximately 215 million non-institutionalized U.S. adults.

52 Measures: HICP was defined per NHIS criteria as chronic pain frequently limiting life or work
53 activities. PA was categorized as no PA, some PA below guidelines, meets aerobic only, and
54 meets both aerobic and muscle-strengthening guidelines.

55 Analysis: Survey-weighted linear probability models estimated adjusted HICP prevalence by PA
56 category. A Wald trend test assessed monotonic association. Modified Poisson regression
57 estimated prevalence ratios (PR) and, with natural cubic splines, modeled continuous dose–
58 response. All models adjusted for age, sex, and race/ethnicity. Sensitivity analyses examined
59 expanded covariates, exclusion of respondents unable to exercise, and subgroup interactions
60 (Supplement 2).

61 Results: Adjusted HICP prevalence decreased from 8.4% (no PA) to 3.9% (some PA), 2.9%
62 (aerobic only), and 2.9% (both guidelines) (trend $p < .001$). Corresponding prevalence ratios
63 were 0.45, 0.33, and 0.26 relative to no PA. Continuous modeling revealed steep HICP
64 reductions at low activity volumes, plateauing beyond approximately 200–300 minutes/week.

65 Results were robust to exclusion of respondents coded as unable to exercise and persisted,
66 though attenuated, after greater adjustments for education, BMI, arthritis, depression, anxiety,
67 and income.

68 Conclusion: Higher PA levels were associated with progressively lower HICP prevalence, with
69 the greatest reductions occurring at the transition from inactivity to any PA.

70 **Keywords:** physical activity, chronic pain, national health interview survey, dose-response,
71 health promotion

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74 **Purpose:**

75 Chronic pain is among the most prevalent and costly health conditions in the United
76 States. National estimates indicate that approximately one in five U.S. adults experiences chronic
77 pain ¹, with annual economic costs estimated between \$560 and \$635 billion in healthcare
78 expenditures and lost productivity ². A subset of individuals with chronic pain, termed high-
79 impact chronic pain (HICP), experience pain that frequently limits life or work activities,
80 affecting an estimated 7–8% of U.S. adults ^{1,3}. The concept of HICP was introduced through the
81 National Pain Strategy to distinguish individuals whose pain substantially restricts participation
82 in daily activities from those with chronic pain that does not produce such functional limitations

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84 Physical activity (PA) is a cornerstone of preventive medicine with well-established
85 benefits for reducing the risk of numerous chronic diseases ⁴. The 2018 Physical Activity
86 Guidelines for Americans recommend that adults engage in at least 150 minutes per week of
87 moderate-intensity aerobic activity or 75 minutes of vigorous-intensity activity, combined with
88 muscle-strengthening activities on two or more days per week ⁴. Emerging evidence also
89 supports PA as a non-pharmacological approach for the management and prevention of chronic
90 pain. Systematic reviews have demonstrated that physical activity interventions can reduce pain
91 severity and improve physical function among adults with chronic pain conditions ^{5,6}. These
92 findings are particularly relevant given ongoing efforts to promote non-pharmacological pain
93 management strategies at the population level.

94 Despite the recognized benefits of PA for chronic pain, population-level evidence
95 examining the relationship between PA and HICP remains limited. The 2020 National Health
96 Interview Survey (NHIS) presents a unique analytical opportunity because it is the only publicly

107 available NHIS survey year that contains both the HICP assessment items and detailed PA
108 frequency and duration variables in the same adult sample^{7,8}. To the authors' knowledge, the
109 association between PA levels and HICP prevalence has not been previously reported using this
110 nationally representative U.S. data. The purpose of this secondary analysis was therefore to
111 examine the dose–response relationship between PA and HICP prevalence among U.S. adults
112 using the 2020 NHIS adult sample data.

113 **Methods:**

114 We conducted a cross-sectional analysis using the 2020 National Health Interview Survey
115 (NHIS) Sample Adult public-use file⁸, a nationally representative survey of the U.S. civilian,
116 non-institutionalized population. Only 2020 was analyzed because the public-use file for that
117 year contains the high-impact chronic pain (HICP) items alongside physical activity (PA)
118 required for our outcome, whereas other years do not due to rotation of measures. Notably, the
119 2020 NHIS transitioned from exclusively in-person to a mixed-mode (telephone and in-person)
120 administration during the COVID-19 pandemic, which may affect data comparability with non-
121 pandemic years.

122 Adults aged ≥ 18 years who completed the Sample Adult questionnaire in 2020 were
123 eligible. We created a complete-case analytic cohort by requiring non-missing values for the
124 survey design variables (WTFA_A, PSTRAAT, PPSU), the HICP outcome, the PA exposure, and
125 covariates retained in the final models.

126 Following NHIS definitions, we first defined chronic pain from the variable
127 PAIFRQ3M_A as pain on most days or every day in the past three months. We then defined
128 HICP as chronic pain that limited life or work most days or every day in the past three months

119 based on PAIWKLM3M_A. Individuals responding 3 or 4 for both criteria are said to have
120 HICP, as defined by the NHIS. Respondents without chronic pain (PAIFRQ3M_A = 1 or 2) were
121 classified as non-HICP regardless of PAIWKLM3M_A, which is not administered to this group.

122 For leisure time physical activity, we constructed moderate-equivalent minutes/week as:

123
$$eq_{\min}^{wk} = (MODFREQW_A \times MODMIN_A) + 2 \times (VIGFREQW_A \times VIGMIN_A)$$

124 [Moderate-equivalent minutes/week = moderate-intensity frequency × moderate-intensity
125 minutes per session) + 2 × (vigorous-intensity frequency × vigorous-intensity minutes per
126 session)]

127 The NHIS frequency-per-week variables (MODFREQW_A, VIGFREQW_A,
128 STRFREQW_A) use special codes to distinguish respondents who never engage in an activity
129 type (code 94), are unable to do so (code 95), or have missing data (codes 96–99 for refused, not
130 ascertained, don't know, or not stated). In the primary analysis, we recoded both 94 (never) and
131 95 (unable) to a frequency of zero and set the corresponding session-duration variables
132 (MODMIN_A, VIGMIN_A) to zero when blank due to skip patterns; codes 96–99 and duration
133 values ≥ 996 were set to missing. Because respondents coded 95 may be unable to exercise due to
134 pain itself, we conducted a sensitivity analysis excluding these individuals (Supplement 2, Table
135 S3). We also used STRFREQW_A (days/week) for muscle-strengthening activity, applying the
136 same recoding scheme. The NHIS does not capture strength training volume (sets, repetitions, or
137 load), limiting this measure to frequency only. Per the 2018 Physical Activity Guidelines for
138 Americans, we created a basic four-level PA category: No PA (moderate equivalent minutes per
139 week= 0); Some PA but below guidelines (> 0 but < 150 min/wk); Meets aerobic only (≥ 150
140 min/wk, but < 2 strength days/week); and Meets aerobic + strength (≥ 150 min/wk and ≥ 2

141 strength days/wk). For continuous dose–response modeling, we capped equivalent minutes per
142 week at 1,500 to reduce leverage from extreme self-reported values; this affected 536
143 respondents (2.0%), and the maximum uncapped value was 15,960 min/wk (Supplement 2, Table
144 S7).

145 We fit a survey-weighted linear probability model (LPM) with HICP as the outcome and
146 PA category as the exposure. The primary model (Model A) adjusted for age, sex, and
147 race/ethnicity as *a priori* demographic confounders, estimating the total association between PA
148 and HICP. Using estimated marginal means with survey degrees of freedom, we obtained
149 adjusted marginal HICP percentages and 95% CIs for each PA category. To assess confounding
150 by health-related and socioeconomic factors, we fit a second model (Model B) additionally
151 adjusting for education, BMI category, arthritis history, depression frequency, anxiety frequency,
152 and income-to-poverty ratio (Supplement 2, Table S2). We note that several Model B covariates,
153 particularly BMI, arthritis, depression, and anxiety, may be mediators on the causal pathway
154 from PA to HICP rather than confounders. Model B estimates should therefore be interpreted as a
155 conservative association after additional adjustment, rather than a causally identified direct
156 effect. Model B used an expanded complete-case sample while Model A results were unchanged
157 when restricted to this same sample (Supplement 2, Table S2).

158 To increase power for a monotonic association, we encoded PA as an ordinal score (0 =
159 No PA to 3 = Meets aerobic + strength) and tested a linear trend in HICP using a Wald test
160 applied to the survey-weighted linear model (adjusted for age, sex, race/ethnicity; Model A).
161 This produced a design-based Wald F statistic with survey degrees of freedom. This ordinal
162 encoding assumes equal spacing between PA categories; the continuous spline model described

163 below relaxes this assumption. We also report the per-category percentage-point change and the
164 implied end-to-end change of HICP for interpretability.

165 We modeled HICP on the log scale using a survey-weighted modified Poisson regression
166 ⁹ with a natural cubic spline (df = 3; internal knots at 50 and 270 moderate-equivalent min/wk,
167 placed at default quantiles; boundary knots at 0 and 1,500) ¹⁰ for capped moderate-equivalent
168 minutes/week and linear adjustment for strength days/week, plus age, sex, and race/ethnicity.
169 From this model we generated adjusted predicted prevalence (and 95% CIs) across moderate-
170 equivalent minutes/week and plotted the curve, ensuring robust standard errors by computing
171 predictions on the link scale and back-transforming to the prevalence scale ¹¹. We also fit a
172 categorical modified Poisson model to estimate adjusted prevalence ratios (PR) with 95% CIs for
173 each PA category relative to no PA, following the approach of Zou ⁹. Strength training days/week
174 were modeled as linear given the limited range of available data (0–7 days).

175 All tests were two-sided with $\alpha = 0.05$. Point estimates reflect the NHANES design weights ⁸;
176 uncertainty was quantified with Taylor series linearization using the survey design degrees of
177 freedom ^{8,11}.

178 All analyses were performed in R v4.5.1 ^{11–17}. The finalized code used to produce the
179 reported outputs is archived on Github ([redacted for peer-review]). This study is reported in
180 accordance with the CROSS guideline ¹⁸; the completed checklist is provided as supplementary
181 material (S1). Additional supplemental analyses—including a missingness comparison (Table
182 S1), expanded covariate models (Table S2), code 95 sensitivity analysis (Table S3), subgroup
183 interaction analyses by age, sex, and race/ethnicity (Table S4), LPM predicted probability
184 diagnostics (Table S5), spline knot documentation (Table S6), and cap justification (Table S7) are

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185 presented in Supplement 2. As the data are publicly available and deidentified, IRB approval is
186 not required.

187 Results:

188 Of the 31,568 adults who completed the 2020 NHIS Sample Adult questionnaire, 4,500
189 were excluded due to missing data: 3,774 lacked a classifiable HICP status, 725 had incomplete
190 PA data, and 1 was missing sex (Figure 1). The final analytic sample comprised 27,068 adults,
191 representing approximately 215 million non-institutionalized U.S. adults after application of
192 survey weights.

193

194 *Figure 1: Respondent Flow Diagram*

195 The weighted mean age was 46.9 years (SD 18.4), 51.4% were female, and the sample
196 was 62.1% non-Hispanic White, 17.5% Hispanic, 11.4% non-Hispanic Black, and 8.3% non-

197 Hispanic other or multiracial (Table 1). The overall weighted HICP prevalence was 4.2% (95%
198 CI 3.9–4.5). Across PA categories, 27.6% of respondents reported no PA, 23.4% reported some
199 PA below guidelines, 24.3% met aerobic guidelines only, and 24.7% met both aerobic and
200 muscle-strengthening guidelines (Table 1). Those in the no PA group were older (mean age 50.2
201 vs. 41.0 years for meets aerobic + strength), more likely to be female (53.7% vs. 43.6%), and
202 more likely to be Hispanic (21.7% vs. 15.9%).

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204 *Table 1: Demographics of Respondent; Values are survey-weighted estimates (WTFA_A) from the*
 205 *complete-case analytic sample. Counts are presented in millions with column percentages in*
 206 *parentheses. Column headers show unweighted sample sizes. Total 2020 Sample Adult*
 207 *respondents (unweighted): 31,568.*

Characteristic	Overall (N = 27,068)	No PA (n = 7,473)	Some PA (n = 6,343)	Aerobic Only (n = 6,579)	Aerobic + Strength (n = 6,673)
Weighted N, millions	215.1	61.5	49.7	49.5	54.4
Age, mean (SD)	46.9 (18.4)	50.2 (19.2)	47.7 (17.9)	48.7 (18.0)	41.0 (16.8)
Sex, %					
Male	104.5 (48.6)	28.5 (46.3)	21.2 (42.7)	24.1 (48.8)	30.7 (56.4)
Female	110.6 (51.4)	33.0 (53.7)	28.5 (57.3)	25.4 (51.2)	23.7 (43.6)
Race/Ethnicity, %					
NH White	133.6 (62.1)	34.4 (55.9)	30.8 (62.1)	32.9 (66.4)	35.5 (65.2)
NH Black	24.6 (11.4)	8.4 (13.7)	5.9 (11.8)	4.6 (9.4)	5.7 (10.4)
NH Asian	1.5 (0.7)	0.7 (1.2)	0.3 (0.6)	0.3 (0.5)	0.2 (0.4)
Hispanic	37.5 (17.5)	13.3 (21.7)	8.0 (16.1)	7.6 (15.3)	8.6 (15.9)
NH Other/Multiracial	17.8 (8.3)	4.6 (7.5)	4.7 (9.4)	4.2 (8.4)	4.4 (8.1)

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209 Unadjusted weighted HICP prevalence was 8.3% among adults reporting no PA, 3.5% for
 210 some PA below guidelines, 2.6% for meeting aerobic guidelines only, and 1.7% for meeting both
 211 guidelines. In models adjusted for age, sex, and race/ethnicity (Model A), the adjusted HICP
 212 prevalence ranged from 8.4% (95% CI 7.3–9.6) among adults reporting no PA to 2.9% (95% CI
 213 1.9–3.9) among those meeting both guidelines (Table 2). Notably, adjusted prevalences were
 214 slightly higher than unadjusted values for the active groups, indicating that demographic
 215 confounding partially masked the unadjusted association. Corresponding prevalence ratios,
 216 relative to no PA, were 0.45 (95% CI 0.38–0.54) for some PA, 0.33 (95% CI 0.26–0.41) for
 217 meeting aerobic guidelines only, and 0.26 (95% CI 0.20–0.34) for meeting both aerobic and

218 strength guideline

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219 *Table 2: Adjusted HICP prevalence by PA category*

PA category	Adj. HICP %	95% CI
No PA	8.441609	7.3–9.6
Some PA but below guidelines	3.905529	2.9–4.9
Meets aerobic only	2.906951	1.9–3.9
Meets aerobic + strength	2.887472	1.9–3.9

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221 Treating PA as an ordinal score (0 = No PA to 3 = Meets aerobic + strength), there was a
 222 significant linear trend toward lower HICP with higher PA (Wald $F(1, 563) = 184.75$, $p < 0.001$).
 223 Each one-category increase in PA corresponded to a 1.82 percentage-point lower adjusted HICP
 224 prevalence (95% CI -2.09 to -1.56). The implied end-to-end difference from No PA to Meets
 225 aerobic + strength was -5.47 percentage points (95% CI -6.26 to -4.68). In an expanded model
 226 additionally adjusting for education, BMI, arthritis, depression, anxiety, and income (Model B;
 227 Supplement 2, Table S2), the per-category change attenuated to -0.90 pp (95% CI -1.17 to
 228 -0.63) but the trend remained highly significant ($p < 0.001$).

229 A spline-based, survey-weighted modified Poisson model showed a nonlinear inverse
 230 association between moderate-equivalent minutes/week and HICP, with a steep decline at low
 231 activity volumes and a flat, low plateau beyond ~ 200 – 300 minutes/week; uncertainty widened at
 232 higher volumes. The predicted curve and 95% CIs are shown in figure 2.

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Adjusted dose–response of HICP across leisure-time PA (NHIS 2020)

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Figure 2. Adjusted dose–response of HICP across leisure-time PA

Discussion:

This cross-sectional secondary analysis examined the association between physical

activity levels and HICP prevalence among a nationally representative sample of U.S. adults.

Using the 2020 NHIS, the only publicly available survey year containing both HICP and detailed

PA measures in the same adult sample, we observed a strong, graded inverse association between

PA and HICP. Adults reporting no PA had an adjusted HICP prevalence of 8.4%, compared to

2.9% among those meeting both aerobic and muscle-strengthening guidelines (PR = 0.26, 95%

CI 0.20–0.34). The continuous dose–response analysis revealed a steep decline in HICP

prevalence at low activity volumes, with a plateau beyond approximately 200–300 moderate-

244 equivalent minutes per week, suggesting that even modest amounts of PA are associated with
245 meaningfully lower HICP prevalence.

246 These findings are consistent with the broader PA–pain literature. Fjeld et al.
247 demonstrated an inverse dose–response relationship between multiple PA measures and chronic
248 pain severity in the population-based Tromsø Study ¹⁹. Systematic reviews have similarly
249 established that PA interventions reduce pain severity and improve physical function among
250 adults with various chronic pain conditions ^{5,6,20}. Proposed biological mechanisms underlying
251 these benefits include exercise-induced hypoalgesia mediated by endogenous opioid and
252 endocannabinoid systems ^{1,22}, reductions in systemic inflammation ^{23,24}, and improvement in
253 central pain processing ²⁵. While the mechanisms underlying the observed association cannot
254 be determined from cross-sectional survey data, our results extend the broader body of evidence
255 linking PA to chronic pain outcomes and do so at the population level using a nationally
256 representative U.S. sample.

257 Additionally, adjusted HICP prevalence was nearly identical among adults meeting
258 aerobic guidelines only and those meeting both aerobic and muscle-strengthening guidelines
259 (2.9% vs. 2.9%; PR = 0.33 vs. 0.26, overlapping CIs). This finding is notable given that
260 systematic reviews have demonstrated associations between resistance training and pain
261 reduction in conditions including low back pain ^{5,27}, fibromyalgia ²⁸, and osteoarthritis ²⁹.
262 However, those trials targeted condition-specific chronic pain rather than HICP as a composite
263 construct, and no studies to date have examined the relationship between resistance training and
264 HICP specifically. Importantly, the NHIS measures muscle-strengthening activity solely as days
265 per week, capturing neither session duration, volume-load, nor exercise type. This crude measure
266 may lack the sensitivity to detect a strength-specific association with HICP beyond what is

267 already captured by aerobic activity. The cross-sectional design further limits interpretation, and
268 future studies using more granular measures of both activity types, including resistance training
269 volume and intensity, are needed to clarify whether strength training confers additional benefits
270 for HICP and to quantify what those benefits are.

271 The observed PA–HICP gradient carries important public health implications. With
272 approximately one in five U.S. adults experiencing chronic pain and 7–8% experiencing HICP³⁰,
273 strategies to reduce pain burden at the population level are urgently needed. These findings are
274 especially relevant given the ongoing need for effective non-opioid approaches to pain
275 management, as emphasized in the updated CDC clinical practice guidelines for prescribing
276 opioids³¹ and the National Institutes of Health’s Helping to End Addiction Over the Long-term
277 (HEAL) initiative³². Exploratory subgroup analyses (Supplement 2, Table S4) indicated that the
278 PA–HICP gradient was strongest among adults aged 40 and older and among women, with
279 significant effect modification by age (interaction $p < 0.001$), sex ($p < 0.001$), and race/ethnicity
280 ($p = 0.013$). The steep initial decline in HICP prevalence at lower PA volumes suggests that
281 public health messaging need not focus solely on meeting full guideline thresholds. Encouraging
282 any PA among currently inactive adults may be associated with the largest differences in HICP
283 prevalence. This is consistent with the 2018 Physical Activity Guidelines Advisory Committee’s
284 conclusion that some PA is better than none⁴.

285 **Limitations:**

286 Several limitations should be considered when interpreting these results. First, the cross-
287 sectional design precludes causal inference. The relationship between PA and HICP is likely
288 bidirectional: while PA may reduce chronic pain, HICP may also limit individuals’ ability to
289 engage in PA. Mendelian randomization studies have begun to disentangle these pathways for

290 specific pain conditions³³, but prospective cohort studies are needed to clarify directionality for
291 HICP. Second, both PA and pain measures are based on self-report, introducing the possibility of
292 recall bias and social desirability bias. Third, the 2020 NHIS was conducted during the COVID-
293 19 pandemic, which may have altered PA patterns, healthcare-seeking behaviors, and pain
294 experiences, potentially limiting generalizability to non-pandemic years⁷. Fourth, the primary
295 model (Model A) adjusted only for age, sex, and race/ethnicity; residual confounding by body
296 mass index, mental health status, socioeconomic position, and comorbid conditions cannot be
297 excluded. On the expanded complete-case sample used for Model B, additional adjustment for
298 education, BMI, arthritis, depression, anxiety, and comorbidity reduced the PA–HICP slope by
299 approximately 30% (Supplement 2, Table S2b), indicating attenuation of the association after
300 accounting for health and socio-economic factors that may act as confounders and/or
301 intermediates. Fifth, we applied a complete-case analytic strategy; a comparison of included
302 versus excluded respondents (Supplement 2, Table S1) showed that excluded individuals were
303 older and had higher HICP prevalence, suggesting our estimates may understate population-level
304 HICP prevalence. Moreover, if excluded respondents were disproportionately both inactive and
305 experiencing HICP, the observed PA–HICP association in the complete-case sample may not
306 fully represent the relationship in the total population. However, the direction and magnitude of
307 this potential bias on the association cannot be determined without PA data for excluded
308 respondents which is the largest reason behind their exclusion. Sixth, recoding respondents who
309 reported being unable to exercise (code 95) as having zero PA could inflate the observed
310 association; however, a sensitivity analysis excluding these individuals (n = 204; Supplement 2,
311 Table S3) yielded virtually identical results. Finally, the linear probability model produced a
312 small proportion (5.7%) of predicted probabilities slightly below zero (minimum -0.027;

313 Supplement 2, Table S5), which is typical for LPMs applied to low-prevalence outcomes and
314 does not materially affect the marginal estimates; the modified Poisson model, which constrains
315 predictions to the positive real line, served as a complementary robustness check.

316 **Conclusion:**

317 In this cross-sectional analysis of a nationally representative sample of U.S. adults, higher
318 PA levels were associated with progressively lower HICP prevalence, with the largest differences
319 observed at the transition from inactivity to any PA. These findings are consistent with the role
320 for PA in non-pharmacological approaches to pain management and add population-level
321 evidence to the PA–pain literature. The 2020 NHIS is the only survey year to date that has
322 included both HICP assessment items and detailed PA measures in the same adult sample,
323 underscoring the need for continued inclusion of these variables in future NHIS iterations. Future
324 research should leverage prospective designs and objective PA measurement to clarify causal
325 pathways, examine whether targeted PA interventions can reduce HICP burden among high-risk
326 populations, and investigate whether the dose–response pattern observed here holds across
327 demographic subgroups and pain-subtypes.

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329 **“SO WHAT?”:**

330 *What is already known on this topic?* Physical activity reduces pain severity in clinical
331 populations with specific chronic pain conditions, but the relationship between PA guideline
332 adherence and high-impact chronic pain at the population level has not been established.

333 *What does this article add?* Using the only nationally representative U.S. dataset containing both
334 measures, this study demonstrates a strong inverse dose–response relationship between PA and
335 HICP, with the steepest reductions occurring at the transition from no activity to any activity.

336 *What are the implications for health promotion practice or research?* Public health messaging
337 around PA for pain prevention need not emphasize full guideline adherence alone. Encouraging
338 any PA among inactive adults may be associated with the largest differences in HICP prevalence.
339 Future NHIS iterations should include both PA and HICP items to enable ongoing surveillance of
340 this relationship.

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